

REECO-SOIL

REECO-SOIL Systematic Literature Review Protocol

Project Acronym: REECO-SOIL

Project Title: Regenerative Retrofitting Via Ecologically Active Soil Structures

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) 2020

1.1 Introduction

A transparent systematic review should present completely and accurately why it has been done, what has been done and what was found. The benefits of a systematic review are:

- They allow researchers to identify future research priorities based on the synthesis of state-of-the-art knowledge in a certain field.
- Questions that cannot be addressed by individual studies can be answered by systematic reviews.
- Give a hint to future studies to rectify aspects of primary research identified on them.
- Provide answers to how and why a particular phenomenon occurs based on the generation and/or evaluation of theories.
- They can generate or evaluate theories about how or why phenomena occur.

The PRISMA 2020 [1] methodology, although mainly developed and used in the medical and clinical sciences, could be also applied in engineering and education, as it provides guidance in methodologies to identify, select, appraise and synthesize the available literature. This document presents the protocol adopted to conduct a systematic literature review with the aim of exploring what the current materials (soil types), methods (application techniques), and biological components (plant species) are used in the literature for integrating ecologically active soils into building retrofitting strategies. It follows the checklist provided by PRISMA and guidelines of the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration [2].

1.2 Protocol

The recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol according to the PRISMA-P methodology [3, 4] are presented in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Administrative information

Title:	
Identification	REECO-SOIL Systematic Literature Review Protocol.
Update	Not applicable, this is a new systematic review.
Registration:	
This protocol has been registered in the OSF Registries website (https://osf.io/registries) under the Generalized Systematic Review Registration Form [5] on 01/05/2025. Its associated project identifier is FGBYW [6] and its corresponding registration number is 9PGZ4 [7].	
Authors:	
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Contributions	Guarantor: AJR. Conceptualization: AJR, JCH. Investigation: AJR, JCH, FJCP. Methodology: AJR, JCH, FJCP. Project Administration: AJR, JCH. Resources: AJR, JCH. Writing – original draft preparation: AJR. Writing – review and editing: AJR, JCH, FJCP.
Amendments	In the event of protocol amendments, the date of each amendment will be accompanied by a description of the change and the rationale. See Annex A.

Support:	
Sources	This project has received funding from RENEW Summer Bursary 2024-2025.
Sponsor	The Centre for Regenerative Design & Engineering for a Net Positive World (RENEW) funded this research.
Role of sponsor/funder	The funder is not involved in any other aspect of the project and will have no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.

Table 2. Introduction.

Rationale:	<p>The global construction sector faces a critical challenge: how to mitigate the environmental footprint of our built environment while adapting to climate change and avoiding further biodiversity loss. It is estimated that approximately 80% of the buildings that will exist in 2050 have already been constructed [8]. Unfortunately, most of these buildings perform poorly in terms of energy efficiency and environmental integration, and they fall short of delivering net-positive outcomes. Net-positive systems actively contribute to the regeneration of ecosystems and human well-being, rather than merely preventing harm, ultimately renewing humans unity with nature [9]. This implies that the window of opportunity for shaping the future performance of the built environment lies not predominantly in new builds, but in the adaptation, retrofitting, and reuse of existing assets. In comparison with the demolition and construction of a new building, retrofitting and reusing an existing one could lead to up to 70 % reduction of the upfront embodied carbon in construction [10].</p> <p>Conventional retrofitting strategies often rely on energy-intensive materials and processes, raising concerns about their long-term sustainability [11]. There is an urgent need to develop regenerative retrofitting approaches. Such approaches need to be holistic and go beyond carbon neutrality to actively restore ecological systems and support human health and comfort, allowing humans and nature to go beyond survival, to thrive, and co-evolve [12].</p> <p>In this context, soil emerges as a powerful yet underexplored ally. Natural soil is a low-embodied energy, healthy, and recyclable material that has been used for millennia in architecture and construction across cultures [13-15]. Rooted in vernacular traditions, earthen construction techniques embody principles of circularity and sustainability [16]. Recent innovations suggest that soil, when designed to be ecologically active, can be reimagined as a dynamic material capable of supporting plant growth [17]. Ecologically active soils—engineered to provide optimal humidity and nutrient conditions—can form living building surfaces that sequester carbon, offer thermal insulation, foster biodiversity, and enhance aesthetics and occupant well-being.</p> <p>Despite growing interest in green infrastructure [18] and nature-based solutions [19], a central challenge persists: how can we integrate green areas into existing buildings in a regenerative and innovative way? While green roofs and living walls have gained some traction, their adoption remains limited due to cost, complexity, and context-specific design constraints. Recent advances in aerial additive manufacturing [20] and 3D printing [21], could foster the potential of activated soil-based retrofitting interventions. A systematic, interdisciplinary understanding of how ecologically active soils can be applied to the retrofitting of the built environment is currently lacking.</p>
Objectives:	<p>The objective of this systematic literature review is to investigate the state-of-the-art and regenerative potential of using ecologically active soil structures to retrofit existing buildings. Specifically, the study addresses the following key question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the current materials (soil types), methods (application techniques), and biological components (plant species) explored in the literature for integrating ecologically active soils into building retrofitting strategies?

Table 3. Methods.

Eligibility criteria:	<p>Peer reviewed records published as Articles, Conference Paper, or Book Chapters, in Journals, Conference Proceedings, Books, or Book Series within the subject areas of Engineering, Materials Science, Environmental Science, and Energy, from 2000 up to 2025, written in English, and containing the following keywords of interest (and similar terms, namely: print* to catch printing, printer, etc.) as part of the record's title, abstract, or keywords, will be initially included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil-Related Keywords: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ soil-based material. ○ ecological soil. ○ ecologically active soil. ○ living soil. ○ bioactive soil.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ engineered soil. ○ earthen. ○ earthen construction. ● Retrofitting and Building Envelope Keywords: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ retrofitting. ○ building retrofit. ○ facade retrofit. ○ building envelope. ○ thermal insulation. ○ sustainable retrofit. ○ green retrofitting. ○ building refurbishment. ● Application Technique Keywords: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3D printing. ○ additive manufacturing. ○ extrusion. ○ robotic extrusion. ○ spraying. ○ spray application. ○ material deposition. ○ automated construction. ○ digital fabrication.
Information sources:	See [22].
Search strategy:	See [22].
Study records:	
Data management	See [22].
Selection process	<p>The selection process will follow the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for systematic reviews [1].</p> <p>All remaining records after deduplication will be screened by two independent reviewers based on title, abstract and keywords. Disagreements on the selection process would be resolved by a third reviewer who will ultimately decide on the selection or rejection of the record.</p> <p>All records remaining from the screening process will be sought for retrieval. Found records will be assessed for eligibility based on the entire content.</p>
Data collection process	Data will be extracted manually using a pre-defined data extraction form and a qualitative summary approach.
Data items:	<p>The data items of interest would be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Material type (soil type, composition, etc.). ● Application technique (e.g., 3D printing, spraying, extrusion). ● Vegetation/seed species. ● Environmental/climatic context (temperature, humidity, etc.). ● Performance outcomes (e.g., thermal insulation, plant viability, etc.).
Outcomes and prioritization:	<p>The primary outcome is the identification of materials and techniques for retrofitting buildings using ecologically active soil structures.</p> <p>Secondary outcomes include soil-plant compatibility, sustainability potential, and innovative fabrication methods.</p>
Risk of bias in individual studies:	As this is not a meta-analysis and includes design/engineering case studies, formal risk of bias tools will not be used. Instead, the risk of bias and quality of individual studies will be assessed based on the prior experience and background knowledge of the authors of the review working on similar reviews on the past and based on reporting transparency and methodological clarity.
Data synthesis:	<p>Both a bibliometric analysis and a narrative synthesis will be performed.</p> <p>The approaches for the bibliometric analysis will be a performance analysis and a science mapping. The performance analysis will be presented in terms of publications per year, most cited authors, most cited records, documents per country, keyword occurrence, and most used source for publication. On the other hand, the science mapping will analyse the co-authorship relationships in terms of authors and countries, as well as the co-occurrence relationships between keywords (both author and index keywords).</p>

	The information of the included records will be qualitatively summarized in a narrative synthesis as the findings are characterized by heterogeneity. The narrative synthesis will be conducted based on thematic analysis. Studies will be grouped by soil type, application method, and retrofitting context.
Meta-bias(es):	Not applicable. No quantitative synthesis is conducted, and publication bias assessment is not feasible in this design-oriented field.
Confidence in cumulative evidence:	No confidence assessment plan will be used for the proposed systematic review. This is based in the fact that no universally accepted methodology is available for the grading of reviewing in the field. The strength of the body of evidence will be assessed qualitatively by considering breadth, consistency, and methodological transparency.

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Annex A

Table 4. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	07/05/2025	Initial version.

